

1 Million Wikipedia Articles

The English Wikipedia is now the largest of the 319 language editions with over 6 million articles and 41 users, This is not the same case with the other language editions, some of these editions are still under a thousand articles only, and some of them are still fighting haters to prove its rights to exist, this is the case of Egyptian Wikipedia.

The Egyptian Arabic Wikipedia edition was proposed on 30 March by a Wikipedian with the username "Ghaly", On 24 November 2008, the Egyptian Arabic Wikipedia was officially launched, since that day, the Egyptian Wikipedia has been subject to controversy, causing arguments between supporters and opponents, opponents perceived the creation of the Egyptian-language Wikipedia as an attack on the Arabic Wikipedia, moreover, some of them claimed it was an organized attack aiming at the Arabic language and Islam, their claims were based on that "Ghaly" and some of the participants were Christians, and that some of the topics of their articles are about Christianity, Discussions and criticism have occurred in some Facebook groups and several blogs and forums that perceived the project to be antagonistic against the Arab identity and Islam, some of the online users stated that they see in Wikipedia Masry yet another Jewish plot.

Regardless of the criticism and the constant vandalizes, and even the requests to close the Egyptian Wikipedia, Egyptian Wikipedia users continued writing articles and developing the project over the years, but this development was slowly moving, so that some users lost hope in trying to convince the haters of the importance of the project and its right to Existence.

In 2019, a new Wikipedia with the username "HitomiAkane" joined Egyptian Wikipedia, he started to add thousands of articles on daily basis without stopping, in three months articles count was over 100 thousand after it was only 25 thousand, a few months later the Egyptian Wikipedia hit the 500 thousand articles milestone, which brought back the story of Egyptian Wikipedia to the spotlights again, the war against it started all over again, many attempts were held to convince this user to go back to Arabic Wikipedia and stop participating in Egyptian Wikipedia, this was not to stop there, the final attempt was to punish him side by side with Ghaly, the stewards of Wikipedia decided to remove his Admin access, and remove Ghaly's Bureaucrat access, in an attempt to make him cut off his participating, this was frustrating for all but didn't stop them, by July 2020, Egyptian Wikipedia hit the 1 million articles and kept increasing frequently month after month.

Until March 2021 no one knew who was "HitomiAkane", his identity remained anonymous, no one even knew if he was a man or woman, where is he from, nothing was clear about him, this all was revealed when he finally released his book, "How I wrote a million Wikipedia articles" by "Maher Asaad Baker", "Maher" was a Syrian software and VFX artist living in Egypt, "Maher", in his book, told the story that led him to write over 1 million Wikipedia articles, he stated that he didn't accept the idea of Wikipedia itself at first, but after he had a heart attack, he had to stay in bed all day long, that made him change his mind about sharing knowledge, he said that reading articles online was his only amusement while he was stuck to his bed, in his book he talked how he started participating in Arabic Wikipedia at first, although he was sick of the way that Arabic Wikipedia was managed, for him it reflected the Arabic reality in general, the project is controlled by prejudiced administrators, He mentioned that the fake conspiracies ideas were what led him to get to know the Egyptian Wikipedia when he started

reading about it in Arabic Wikipedia, the idea of a "Ghaly" conspiracy to attack the Arabic language and Islam was as funny as it made him participate in it to know what was going on, he says that his natural reaction to this The prejudices of Arab users against the Egyptian Wikipedia project made him fully believe that it was right, "Maher" explained in his book how he collected, manage and automate the articles creation process, and how eventually could add more than 1 million articles in addition to other improvements he made in the project, based on his programming skills, "Maher" included some of the SQL statements the codes scripts he used in his own work so anyone could understand the process and do it.

By today Egyptian Wikipedia is over 1,200,000 articles, and there is no magical solution here as he stated in his final words in the book, the process is time-consuming, and above that, it needs a strong determination, but after all the process is doable as long as you do what you love and enjoy doing it.

Maher Asaad Baker

<https://www.amazon.com/dp/B08XZTYLHN>

How I wrote a million Wikipedia articles

